

(the mycelium is produced in liquid media and later sporulates on solid substrates).

We used a method to produce dry mycelium particles (the marcescent process). Fungi are grown in fermentors in liquid media and the mycelium dried and ground into small particles (0.5-0.7 mm diam). The mycelium can be applied in the field, where it sporulates on the rice plant. Conidia produced in the field infect pest insects.

Storage of dried mycelium can be a problem. We tested the optimum storage conditions for mycelium of a *B. bassiana* (Bals.) Vuill. strain originating from BPH in China.

Mycelium was produced in 15-liter bubbler-type airlift fermentors in a saccharose (3%) - yeast extract (1%) medium. After 3 d growth, mycelium was harvested by filtration and dried to 7-10% moisture content, using forced air and the desiccant calcium oxide.

Four storage temperatures (-20, 5, 25, and 35 °C) and 7 storage times (0, 1, 2, 4, 8, 16, and 32 wk) were tested in 3 replications. Each replication was a small airtight tube holding 300 mg mycelium particles.

To evaluate regeneration, mycelia were incubated for 3 d on moist filter paper in small petri dishes; conidia were

Numbers of conidia produced per mg of *E. bassiana* mycelium stored at different temperatures for different periods, IRRI, 1988. Bars represent standard deviation.

harvested in a Tween 80^(R) 0.02% solution, counted with standard hemocytometer techniques, and number of conidia produced per mg mycelium calculated.

With 5 °C treatment, sporulation at 2, 4, 8, and 32 wk differed from initial sporulation (see figure). At 32 wk, about 75% of the original amount of conidia was produced. At 25°C, significantly fewer conidia were produced after 2 wk;

after 8 wk, all mycelia were dead. At 35°C, virtually no viable mycelia were left after 1 wk.

We conclude that dry *B. bassiana* mycelium can be stored for a long period only at <-15 °C. Because storage at room temperature is important in commercial development, new formulations with better storage properties are needed. □

Yield losses in floating rice caused by stem borers (SBs)

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To measure SB damage in floating rice, we grew Jalmagna rice plants in 100 pots for several weeks. Plants were thinned to 5/pot, then set 3 m apart in a 100-m² field 5-6 wk before flooding. At maturity, the plants were cut off at the base. SB damage, grain weight, and number of healthy panicles/ pot were recorded (22 pots damaged by rats were excluded).

Damage was categorized as 0-20, 21-40, 41-60, 61-80, and 81-100% (see table). Grain weight declined

The effect of stem borer damage on yield and yield components of Jalmagna.^a Ghagharaghat, India.

Damaged stems (%)	Total pots (no.)	Grain Wt (g/pot)	Healthy panicles (no./pot)
0-20	12	3.56 a	5.5 a
21-40	27	3.20 b	5.1 a
41-60	21	3.03 c	3.5 ab
61-80	14	2.82 d	1.6 bc
81-100	4	2.05 e	0.0 c
cv (%)		2.5	33.9

^aIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

significantly, from 3.6 g/pot with 0-20% SB damage to less than 2.8 g/pot with more than 60% damage—an estimated 32% yield reduction. □

Comparison of sweep net sampling patterns for estimating population density of green leafhopper (GLH)

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Sweep net sampling is the usual method for estimating GLH population density in rice. The action threshold for controlling GLH is based on the number of insects caught in 10 sweeps using a standard 30-cm-diam, 1.5-m-long sweep net.

We tested three sweep net sampling patterns in Carmen, Bohol, Aug-Nov 1987: parallel, along the edge of the field; center, through the center of the

field; and diagonal, diagonally across the field, with 2 replications.

Sampling was done weekly from seedling stage until 60 d after transplanting in 20- × 50-m plots planted to IR64. No insecticide was applied.

Samples were obtained by sweeping while walking at a normal pace along the prescribed pattern. Sampling was done early in the morning. Three 10-sweep samples were taken for each plot—the first from the edge of the plot toward the middle, the second in the middle, and the third from the middle toward the end of the plot.

Density estimates for GLH population were similar, regardless of the sampling pattern (see figure). □

GLH (no./10 sweeps)

Density estimates of GLH population monitored by sweep net sampling along a fixed path in each of the 3 sweep net sampling patterns evaluated in field plots planted to IR64. Carmen, Bohol, Philippines, Aug-Nov 1987.

Yield losses due to rice gall midge (GM)

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When heavy GM *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood Mason) infestation occurred in seed plots at experimental stations in 1987-88 wet season, we took the opportunity to study yield losses.

Yield losses caused by GM. Batalagoda, Sri Lanka, 1987-88 wet season.

Cultivar	Regression equation (yield in g/hill)	Regression ^a (r value)	% yield loss/% incidence
Bg 3-5	$Y = 28.08 - 0.265 X$	0.49**	0.92
Bg 38	$Y = 20.08 - 0.110 X$	0.33*	0.52
Bg 400-1	$Y = 18.61 - 0.20 X$	0.65**	1.07
Bg 379-2	$Y = 26.76 - 0.230 X$	0.59**	0.85
Bg 34-6	$Y = 10.821 - 0.065 X$	0.43 ^{ns}	0.60
Bg 350	$Y = 7.18 - 0.056 X$	0.35 ^{ns}	0.78
Bg 94-1	$Y = 9.67 - 0.028 X$	0.24 ^{ns}	0.29
Bg 34-8	$Y = 15.87 - 0.14 X$	0.36*	0.88
Bg 276-5	$Y = 12.56 - 0.11 X$	0.42*	0.89

^a Significant at the 1% (**) and 5% (*) levels. ns = not significant.

Number of tillers and number of silvershoots were recorded at flowering in 100 randomly tagged hills of 9 cultivars.

The regression between grain

yield/hill on GM incidence (GMI) was calculated. Grain yields were negatively correlated with GM in all cultivars (see table). □

Effect of flooding on Malayan black bug (MBB) egg hatching and parasitoid emergence

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The MBB *Scotinophara coarctata* lays its eggs at the base of rice plants. We studied the effects of flooding on unparasitized eggs and eggs parasitized by *Telenomus triptux*

To determine the effects of flooding on egg hatching, egg masses were put in test tubes filled with water for 0, 6, 12, 18, 24, and 36 h, in 10 replications. To determine the effect of submergence on parasitoid emergence, freshly laid eggs of MBB were placed in a parasite colony

for 24 h. After parasitoid oviposition, the eggs were submerged for 0, 2, 6, 12, 18, 24, and 36 h.

When egg masses were not submerged, 96% hatched; none hatched after submergence for 24 h (see figure). When submerged 6, 12, and 18 h, only 33, 29, and 3% hatched, respectively. Unparasitized eggs submerged for 24 h did not hatch. However, more than 50% of the parasitoids emerged after 24 h submergence (see figure). □

Effect of pesticides on germination and growth of three fungi of rice insects

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Populations of rice brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål) in the field and in insect-rearing cages are commonly infected with specific fungi (Deuteromycotina: Hyphomycetes). Conidia of the fungi germinate on the insect cuticle, and penetration follows. The mycelium multiplies in the hemocoel by yeast-like budding.

Effect of flooding on MBB egg hatchability and parasitoid emergence. IRRI, 1988.